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QUESTIONNAIRE

Date 15.04.2025

Unit name	University of Valencia
Country	Spain
Number of researchers	8000
Number of students	50 000
Link to the website	https://www.uv.es/uvweb/college/en/university-valencia-1285845048380.html
Characteristics of research activities (max. 300 words)	<p>The University of Valencia (UV) is a national first-rate academic institution that also has an important international projection. It appears in good positions within the most prestigious rankings (Source SAP UV).</p> <p>It was positioned among the best 200-300 universities in the world and the 2-4 in Spain, according to the Xangai Ranking 2014. Regionally speaking, the UV is a large centre of scientific production that entails more than 30% of scientific publications in all fields in the Valencian Community, according to Web of Science (Source: ACCIDI Report 2012 “Scientific Research and Technological Development in the Valencian Community”).</p> <p>The UV has a generalist interests and therefore its research addresses all the fields of knowledge: Humanities, Basic Sciences and Engineering, Health Sciences, Social Sciences and Education. In terms of its organisation, the Regulations set out that: “The structure must be organised individually in research units, departments, university research institutes, other UV specialised or joint centres and other private or state organisms.”</p> <p>In this sense, the Regulation that indicates the procedure for creating new UV research structures establishes a legal framework for the creation of research groups, interdisciplinary research structures (ERI) and university research institutes (institutes) as integrated structures for research groups.</p>

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	<p>The University of Valencia of today is the outcome of more than five centuries of history that have led to the accumulation of knowledge and unique documentary treasures, making it one of the top Spanish universities.</p> <p>Initially dedicated to the studies of medicine, humanities, theology and law, the university has witnessed over the past two decades an accelerated process of transformation and growth, something incomparable to earlier periods. This significant effort has turned the University of Valencia into a modern, global university. It has become a leader when it comes to the application of new technologies, connected to important international scientific and teaching networks.</p> <p>The University of Valencia has become one to the top five scientific centres in Spain thanks to its commitment to excellence and to the wide range of teaching and research activities offered in all areas of knowledge (basic sciences and engineering, health sciences, educational sciences, humanities and social sciences, economics and law).</p>
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Does your institution have a formal system for assessing researchers?

Yes

No

If so:

	What document (Rector's ordinance, Senate resolution, national regulations) regulates the researchers assessment system?
1.	At the University of Valencia, the researchers' assessment system is primarily regulated at the national level. The evaluation criteria are part of a national assessment framework, which is updated annually to reflect new policies and standards. In addition to these yearly updates, there is a comprehensive national evaluation conducted every six years.
	What time frame of work is taken into account in the assessment?
2.	In accordance with the Constitution of the University of Valencia, the Departments, Institutes and Interdisciplinary Research Structures draw up an annual report on the research activities carried out. The Research Committee evaluates the Research Reports in accordance with the scale for the distribution of

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	research grants approved by the Governing Council, which ensures the quality and veracity of the information collected.
	What are the basic assessment criteria?
3.	The basic assessment criteria at the University of Valencia are highly structured and comprehensive. They include citation metrics, often normalized by discipline to ensure fairness across fields. Additional indicators include the number of mentions, publications in high-impact journals, and a strong emphasis on internationalization—such as participation in international projects, collaborations, and mobility. Moreover, the use of the institutional repository is mandatory, and researchers are required to deposit their publications, particularly those published from 2023 onwards.
	Do the criteria or their importance differ for job groups (assistant/assistant professor/professor) and/or scientific disciplines?
4.	The criteria are visible in the GREC platform, but they are ultimately used for the institutional-level evaluation
	How are researchers informed about the assessment system and rules?
5.	Researchers are informed about the assessment rules through the GREC online platform, which includes clear guidance on the procedures and criteria. The current rules are still based on the Rector's Ordinance from 2019, though there are ongoing discussions about updating it.
	Do scientists have an influence on determining the principles of assessment?
6.	In practice, researchers have little real influence on defining the assessment principles. The system is largely determined at the national level, with limited opportunities for bottom-up input.
	Do they receive feedback after the assessment (in what form – written/oral)?
7.	The research staff of the University of Valencia annually reports the research activities carried out. From the information included in the individual curricula vitae of the researchers, the scientific production is extracted to enable the report of each department. Yes, researchers receive written feedback through an online platform, where they can view their individual evaluation profile and results or institute to be drawn up.
	Do you use electronic tools to assess scientific achievements?
8.	For the introduction of scientific production data, the UV has the computer application CURRICUL@ of the GREC Platform. It is an application developed by the University of Barcelona and is currently used by several institutions and research bodies in the Valencian Community, Catalonia and the Balearic Islands. The CURRICUL@ application allows you to update and manage your own CV, as well as export it in various formats, including the CVN format (Standardised Curriculum Vitae) developed by the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) of the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO).

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	Are there any automated elements in the assessment system, e.g. is there a possibility to generate achievements report from the employee portal?
9.	<p>Based on the individual scientific production reported annually by researchers of the University, and evaluated by the Research Committee (see section "GREC - data introduction"), the individual Scientific Production Index or SPI is elaborated.</p> <p>This indicator makes it possible to analyse and evaluate the University's research activity, with the aim of prioritising strategies, designing policies, evaluating research structures and allocating resources for research and knowledge transfer.</p> <p>The individualised information is available only for research staff in the SPI application.</p>
	Does the assessment of scientific achievements take into account bibliometric indicators??
10.	<p>Yes, bibliometric indicators play a significant role. Points are awarded for publications in journals ranked in Scimago Journal Rank (SJR), and citations are also taken into consideration.</p>
	Do the assessment criteria take into account elements considered as Open Science?
11.	<p>There is an incentive to deposit publications in the institutional repository (via GREC), and the system promotes visibility and accessibility. However, Open Science elements are not yet systematically integrated as formal criteria in the assessment.</p>
	How often is the assessment system changed or modified and for what reason (legislative changes or under the influence of opinions?)
12.	<p>The system is updated annually in terms of internal assessment for funding purposes, but the core regulatory document (Rector's Ordinance) from 2019 has remained unchanged. Planned changes are driven mostly by strategic or legislative needs, not directly by researchers' feedback.</p>
	Is the result of the assessment associated with a promotion, contract extension or other element, such as a salary increase?
13.	<p>Assessment results do not directly affect employment status (e.g., no automatic dismissal), but they are used to allocate internal funding and subsidies. Researchers with stronger outputs may receive increased internal financial support.</p>
	Are the criteria for scientific assessment related to the implementation of the university's strategy/vision/mission?
14.	<p>Yes, the results feed into the Scientific Production Index (SPI), which helps guide the university's strategic priorities, design research policies, and evaluate research units for resource allocation and planning.</p>

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Are the most prestigious ERC grants particularly recognized and promoted in the assessment of scientific activity?	
15.	While not explicitly stated, major international grants, such as ERC grants, are highly valued and contribute significantly to a researcher's standing within the SPI and internal rankings. They are used as indicators of excellence and international competitiveness.

If no:

1.	What does the assessment process for researchers look like?
2.	What are the assessment rules?
3.	Despite the lack of a formal system, do researchers know the principles of assessment?
4.	Are there any consequences after the assessment of academic staff is completed, and if so, what are they?
5.	Do you intend to implement a formal system for assessing scientists in the future?